

Unique or Ubiquitous: Information Literacy Instruction Outside Academia

Abstract

Purpose: To investigate how U.S. public libraries offer information literacy (IL) instruction to their patrons.

Design/methodology: A content analysis of eight library websites to determine 1) passive information literacy instruction and 2) active literacy instruction.

Results: Library web guides offer passive information literacy instruction by highlighting resources patrons may wish to access to resolve information inquiries. Further, we found that a little less than 50% of library programming offers some IL instruction, the majority of which relates to helping patrons learn to use tools to create information products.

Originality/value: Information literacy is the ability to recognize the need for information, to effectively find information to meet that need, and to use information for some purpose or goal. Academic, school, and public libraries believe that understanding and using information critically and effectively bring gains to an individual and to society. However, they diverge in how and why they engage in IL instruction. Our findings suggest that less than half of the libraries surveyed are providing active IL instruction, despite the recognition of the benefits IL provides.

Keywords: Information literacy instruction, public libraries, critical information literacy.

1 Introduction

Information literacy (IL) is the ability to recognize the need for information, to effectively find information to meet that need, and to use information for some purpose or goal. Historically, information literacy was important for well-informed, civic discourse, as well as for preparing people to be productive workers (O'Connor, 2009). More recently, critical perspectives have emerged that view IL as a way for learners to understand systems of power around information and develop a critical consciousness of learning (Elmborg, 2006).

Both academic and public libraries believe that understanding and using information critically and effectively bring gains to an individual and to society. However, they diverge in how and why they engage in IL instruction, partly due to differences in mission and user base. The purpose of the

academic library, to support the mission of the university, is more formally linked to instruction than that of a public library, even though many public libraries describe themselves and their purpose with education-based language such as being the people's university, or supporting lifelong learning. The value libraries place on their instructional role, as well as their understanding of patrons' motivation and purpose, will direct why and how they facilitate IL instruction. Academic libraries operate under formal structures evidenced by "instruction librarian" job titles, formal courses, modules, and teaching materials, and shared definitions and frameworks for operationalizing information literacy. In contrast, public library IL instruction may be less structured with greater freedom and creativity for delivering IL instruction. However, both types of libraries fulfill important functions in fostering an engaged citizenry, and many patrons experience both of these environments at different times, or even simultaneously, in their lives.

In this paper we first give a high-level overview of conceptual literature comparing public and academic library IL instruction. Then we report on part one of a research study that investigated formal IL instruction at a set of public libraries in two major metropolitan areas in Ohio. We conclude with suggestions for future research. We've intentionally limited our focus to IL instruction practices to adults, defined as people over 18, to remove age as a variable. We acknowledge that IL instruction is a critical concept for K-12 students and direct readers to the literature of school librarianship and children and youth services in public libraries for complete treatment of this age group.

2 Literature Review

Academic and public libraries are fundamentally similar in their purpose: they both seek to collect and disseminate information to meet their communities' information needs. Part of meeting community needs includes the elements associated with developing information literacy. As a formal construct IL has received significantly greater attention in the professional literature of academic librarianship than in public librarianship, and thus, the definitions, standards, and frameworks most associated with IL come from that body of scholarship. The Association for College and Research Library's (ACRL) Framework for Information Literacy for Higher Education (Association for College and Research Libraries, 2015) the Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL) Seven Pillars of Information Literacy Core Model for Higher Education (Society of College, National and University Libraries, 2011), and Secker and Coonan's A New Curriculum for Information Literacy (ANCIL) (Secker and Coonan, 2011) are a few examples of the development of IL as a formal construct in academic libraries. In contrast, the public library professional literature lacks such formal treatment of information literacy. Certainly there are studies, many reported at the European Conference on Information Literacy (ECIL), on how public libraries are engaged in information and/or digital literacy instruction. However, the research literature on public libraries has lagged behind that of academic libraries in developing formal constructs, models, or agendas. In the United States, the primary professional association serving public libraries, Public Library Association (PLA), does not currently offer any documents or position papers about information literacy. A review of programs offered at the most recent PLA conference in 2018 results in only a single program tagged with information literacy.

Scholarly debates surrounding information literacy in the U.S. have resided primarily in the context of higher education. The adoption of the Information Literacy Competency Standards for Higher

Education (Standards) by the American Library Association in 2000 promoted information literacy as an autonomous set of skills to be imparted upon students as part of their formal education. While the Standards were officially rescinded and replaced by the ACRL Framework fifteen years later to reflect the complexity of the information world in which students exist within and outside of the educational setting, public libraries in the U.S. lack the adoption of such formal frameworks for information literacy, although they are widely regarded as institutions of lifelong learning and viewed as “a natural extension of the formal education process” (Jehlik, 2004). Harding (2008) sees the lack of a framework in public libraries as a disadvantage but argues that they are well positioned to provide information literacy because of being places of (informal) learning often over the lifetime (and life transitions) of their community members. Hall criticizes the Public Library Association’s 2005 strategic plan for not going far enough in promoting public libraries as “a central agent in empowering an informed and democratic society” through adopting information literacy (Hall, 2010, p. 171). This critique is grounded in critical information literacy as espoused by Elmborg, which seeks to disrupt the hegemonic structures in which individuals and communities interact with information in order to support true democratic engagement and social justice (Elmborg, 2006, 2012).

Despite the absence of a formal framework, others posit that public libraries, in fact, are very much engaged in information literacy in the spirit of the Alexandria Proclamation, but do not typically use the term itself, “as it does not mean much to the general public” (Widdowson and Smart, 2013, p. 161; World Summit on the Information Society, n.d.). Indeed, many scholars outside of the U.S. acknowledge the importance of the Prague Declaration and the Alexandria Proclamation in recognizing information literacy as a human right and the need to develop community information literacy as the “application of information literacy in community contexts” (Partridge et al., 2008, p.

111). Examples of this can be seen in Seneviratne's research in rural Sri Lanka, and the Australian case studies presented by Partridge, Bruce and Tilley (Partridge et al., 2008; Seneviratne, 2004)

Hall argues that "public librarians may actually be better positioned than school or college librarians to embody the role of teacher-student and stimulate critical information literacy because they have no formalized system of information production and consumption" (Hall, 2010, p. 171). Indeed, based on their research in Canadian public libraries, Julien and Hoffman report that public librarians regard themselves as "teachers/agents of empowerment" and "public parent" (Julien and Hoffman, 2008, p. 32). Frequent one-on-one interaction in public libraries offers the opportunity for "teachable moments" where librarians are able to foster their patrons' critical engagement with information to meet individual needs, whether for the purpose of education or entertainment, and to support civic participation in their communities and beyond. Jacobsen, for example, is teaching information skills in the context of fantasy football in hopes that these may transfer to areas that have higher stakes in the social, political and economic fabric of the community (Jacobsen, 2017). He advocates for "broadening our scope of information literacy and building from our community's strengths and interests—a 'spoonful of sugar' approach" (Jacobsen, 2017, p. 23). Other recent examples of public libraries' espousal of information literacy are outreach events and classes about financial literacy and fake news which often occur in collaboration with school or academic libraries (Ireland, 2017). Unlike an academic setting, classroom instruction in public libraries is not driven by a curriculum but should be regarded as an extension of the one-on-one interaction with reference librarians, where the instructor serves as facilitator, as in the Learning Circles at the Chicago Public Library described by Vercelletto (O'Connell and Haven, 2013; Vercelletto, 2017). In sum, a scan of the literature reveals that despite the absence of a formal framework for information literacy in public

libraries, instruction and outreach events do incorporate IL concepts, albeit, on a smaller scale than is typically seen in academic and school libraries.

While librarians have a long-established history teaching and raising awareness of the ideas of information literacy, similar movements have also been afoot in other fields. Mackey and Jacobson's (2011) seminal article on metaliteracy was one of the early theoretical papers to explore the how technology and more specifically social media and connectedness was changing the idea of information literacy from a set of discrete skills to a broader notion of both using and creating information while interacting with others through mediated technologies. In presenting their notion of metaliteracy, they articulate the subtle distinctions among the concepts of media literacy, digital literacy, visual literacy, and cyber literacy and argue that metaliteracy is a foundation that unifies these related notions of literacies while also incorporating the role technology plays in becoming information literate. More recently, information literacy is intersecting with events in the public sphere stemming from the 2016 presidential election and subsequent attack on news media.

Between the intentional placement of mis- and dis-information in social media channels by Russian hackers, and the president of the United States decrying "fake news" when receiving unfavorable coverage by the media, we find ourselves operating in a "post-truth" society (Bluemle, 2018; Cooke, 2017; Neely-Sardon and Tignor, 2018). Post truth refers to the phenomenon where personal or emotional beliefs are more powerful in shaping a person's understanding than are objective facts or accepted, shared truths (Bluemle, 2018). In this environment, the need for information literacy knowledge and practices is all the more critical (Batchelor, 2017; Ireland, 2018). Of course, librarians are not the only people concerned with the challenges of a "post-truth" world. Journalists are on the front lines of the battle to report accurate, truthful information and have to be more diligent than ever in their own reporting practices. A recent symposium at Simmons College acknowledged the

need for broader collaboration across disciplines and brought together librarians, journalists and folks from allied professions to collaborate on ideas to address the challenges a post-truth world presents. More than 70 attendees worked together over a two-day event to share ideas about new ways to enhance the publics' understanding of "news" and to develop ideas for cross-disciplinary projects to address mis- and dis-information in media (Saunders et al., 2018).

Even though Information literacy may be more prominently promoted in academic settings, given the complexities of the information landscape and the threat of nefarious forces attempting to disrupt that landscape, there is clearly a need to continue the work of helping people at all stages of life understand, evaluate and interpret information.

3 Research

To explore empirically how IL is carried out in public libraries we conducted part one of a research agenda investigating how eight libraries located in two major metropolitan areas of Ohio practice IL instruction. Our guiding question centered on how public library programming incorporates ideas of information literacy.

3.1 Research Design

We conducted a content analysis of eight library system websites looking specifically for examples of 1) passive IL instruction through instructional materials presented on webpages, and 2) active instruction through programming.

3.2 *Sample*

We chose to focus our exploration of IL instruction on a set of public libraries in the state of Ohio. Ohio ranks at or near the top of the US in a number of key metrics related to public library use. Data from the 2013 Institute of Museum and Library Services Public Library Survey, summarized in a report by Howard Fleeter and Associates compiled in April 2016, show that Ohio ranks second in the number of registered borrowers as a percentage of population with 77.8% of the population possessing a library card (Bluemle, 2018; Cooke, 2017; Neely-Sardon and Tignor, 2018). Ohio is also ranked second in the total number of library transactions per year (over 234 million transactions), a category that includes reference interactions, circulation counts, attendance at library programs, and the number of Internet terminal uses. This volume of library use is almost four times the number of transactions as the national average, and places Ohio first in the number of transactions per person (20.33). Ohio is also ranked first in the number of public library visits per capita with 7.50. In parallel with the high use of Ohio public libraries, Ohio libraries per capita operating expenditures are also highly ranked at number three in the US (\$58.52). However, dividing the total operating expenditures by the number of usage transactions puts Ohio's cost per transaction at \$2.88 which falls well below the national average. With this overview of services and funding it is reasonable to expect that public libraries in Ohio may have the desire for and resources available to offer some amount of IL instruction.

Public library systems from two major metropolitan areas were chosen for inclusion in the study. From the Columbus area the libraries are Bexley Public Library, Columbus Metropolitan Library, Grandview Heights Public Library, Upper Arlington Public Library, Westerville Public Library, and Worthington Public Library. From the Cleveland area we included Cleveland Public Library and Cuyahoga County Public Library. This collection of public libraries is diverse in terms of the overall

size of the systems ranging from a single branch system (Bexley) to 27 branches within the Cleveland and Cuyahoga County systems. The libraries collectively all serve primarily urban and suburban areas.

3.3 *Procedures*

Each of the library websites was examined following data collection procedures that included browsing and searching. We first searched within the programming events calendar for each library system identifying any programs targeting adults that might incorporate information literacy content of skills. We used a broad understanding of information for determining inclusion. Any program that might talk about any aspect of having a need for, looking for, retrieving, analyzing, or using information for any purpose was included. As an example, a program entitled “Food Preservation 101” was included as were several instances of open programs like “borrow a librarian” with no specific topic pre-determined. We then also browsed the library system websites for links pointing to web-based instructional guides that might include some aspect of IL instruction. We placed no limit on the subject matter of the guide and included all guides that dealt with any aspect of information literacy. Finally, we also searched within the library websites for the specific phrase “information literacy” located anywhere across the website. However, none of the eight library websites returned any hits on the exact phrase “information literacy”.

Each program and web guide were inductively coded by program content area (e.g., social media, personal finance), skill area (e.g., word processing skills, networking skills) and then assigned a ranking of 1-3 where 1 indicated a clearly stated aspect of information literacy, 2 indicated the item likely contained some part of information literacy, and 3 did not contain information literacy

knowledge or skills. If the program or web guide was coded having some IL content (codes 1 or 2) we then assigned a code representing what aspect of information literacy was addressed. We purposely did not use any of the specific models and frameworks such as the ACRL Framework or Big6 created to represent information literacy in certain populations or types of libraries (Association for College and Research Libraries, 2015; Eisenberg and Berkowitz, n.d.). These were rejected because we found they aligned too closely with scholarly or academic work and were not a good match for the kinds of programming we observed in public libraries. Instead, we used a unifying framework of IL, named the Fundamental Process Model, which integrates the essential elements of IL into four functional areas: *plan*, *access*, *judge*, and *communicate* (Smith and Matteson, 2018). One or more of these four categories were assigned to any program or web guide determined to contain some IL-related content.

4 Limitations

A number of limitations are worth mentioning. First, the sample of libraries chosen for inclusion do not represent a complete range of community types. For example, none of the libraries included are situated in fully rural environments, which may bias the type of programming offered. Second, the analysis of the presence of IL content was carried out based on brief descriptions provided on the library websites. It is possible that IL instruction is occurring within certain programs even if the description does not seem to indicate so.

5 Results

The results of the content analysis are reported here, starting first with the examples of passive instruction in the form of web guides and then reporting the analyses of program offerings.

5.1 *Web-based instructional guides results*

Searching the eight library websites in April 2018 yielded 132 web-based library guides across 6 library sites. In each case, the libraries followed a structured approach to their web guides, relying on a consistent format and function with each guide. The purpose of the guides was to identify and provide access to resources on a particular topic. The resources included print and digital content and also included items considered to be owned or subscribed to by the library as well as freely available items on the Internet. The topics of the guides covered a variety of interest areas such as art, business, genealogy, government information, health, jobs, literature, science, sports, travel, taxes, and voter information.

All 132 of the web guides were coded as being a passive form of information literacy instruction, addressing *access*, according to the Fundamental Process Model. They were deemed passive because they did not contain overt instructional information about how to locate, search, or use the materials included. They fall into the *access* category because they serve to link a library patron with a source of information.

5.2 *Programming results*

The results of the program analysis provide a more detailed depiction of IL instruction in public libraries. Of the eight library systems included, only one did not list any programs during the period

of time searched that were deemed to contain elements of IL instruction for adults. Table 1 lists the libraries and the number of programs included in the analysis.

TABLE 1 HERE

The programs covered a wide range of topics. Technology topics were prevalent at most of the libraries, including programs on cloud computing, social media, online privacy, content streaming services, software skills, coding, operating systems, and learning to use devices. Everyday life topics included taxes, legal questions, personal finances, health and wellness, aging, resume building and job seeking. Programs were also offered on hobby interests such as gardening, literature, art, photography, American history and genealogy. Most programs focused on helping participants develop particular skills related to the topic of instruction, but in a few cases, the programs were geared more toward lecture with discussion instruction format.

Of the 132 programs identified, 70 were determined to include no IL instruction, 59 were determined to likely have some elements of IL instruction, and only 3 were assessed as being entirely focused on an aspect of information literacy.

Within the 62 programs that contained elements of information literacy the predominant Fundamental Processes addressed were *access* and *communicate*. Table 2 shows the distribution of programs by the four Fundamental Processes. (The total is slightly larger than the total number of programs because one program covered more than one element of IL.)

TABLE 2 HERE

A break out of the kinds of programs offered within each area is provided next. Tables 3-5 report the types and numbers of programs for the three Fundamental Process Model areas.

TABLE 3 HERE

TABLE 4 HERE

TABLE 5 HERE

6 Discussion

These results reveal that the public libraries included in this study offer robust programming to their communities. The number and range of programs demonstrates the libraries' commitment to serving their constituents' information needs. In particular, the emphasis placed on technology topics is noteworthy. Public libraries are clearly filling a gap in our technology-centered society helping people understand and use the multiple digital products they encounter on a daily basis. The presence of makerspaces—a 10-year plus phenomenon in libraries—can also be seen in these results (“A Brief History of Makerspaces”, 2015). In this snapshot of programming, there were makerspace classes for using Cricut machines, 3D printing, laser engraving, audio and video converting programs, and 3D modeling and design. Although we cannot conclude from this small sample that this diversity of programming is available in all public libraries, it does reveal that libraries continue to embrace their role in providing educational and fun experiences to their communities.

In spite of the breadth of programming in the data set, the analysis suggests that the public libraries studied here carry out little direct and active IL instruction. We identified only three library programs that were entirely focused on an element of IL. Many libraries did provide passive instruction in the

form of well-designed guides to materials which fulfill the *access* Fundamental Process Model of IL. Though this type of passive instruction does not permit direct instruction because it is asynchronous, it does provide a piece of information literacy.

Beyond the three programs that specifically covered evaluating information sources, there were 59 other programs that contained some element of IL. It is noteworthy that within this subset, the largest number of programs were categorized in the *communicate* Fundamental Process Model of IL. Programs that provided instruction on how to use analog and digital tools to help patrons express themselves and create new content were all coded as *communicate* in that they helped attendees learn to use a particular tool that could be used to present their creative and intellectual work to the world. This finding—that public libraries are putting programming effort toward helping users learn to communicate in a variety of media is consistent with other literature. A European Parliament Committee on Culture and Education report from 2016 on how public libraries promote information and media literacy argues that while the idea of information literacy is seen as focusing mostly on information as fact-based content, regardless of the form, media literacy extends to an understanding of the need for critical consideration of how we interact with information across all media, in all forms or channels. Using a broader conceptualization such as media literacy acknowledges the good work many public libraries are already doing in the direction of supporting patrons' creation of information objects using digital technologies in media-rich environments.

The next largest category of programs were those coded as *access* according to the Fundamental Process Model. This finding was expected, as the knowledge and skills associated with accessing information have traditionally been taught in IL curricula. Here is where the public libraries mirrored most closely their academic and school library counterparts. Finally, only a few programs included

the *judge* component of IL, although, those few were also the programs where the entire purpose of the program was to address the knowledge and skills around evaluating information. Although there were few, these programs are similar to the type of instruction delivered in academic settings. Not surprisingly, no programs were identified that appeared to address the *plan* element of the Fundamental Process Model of IL. We speculate that this is likely because many public library users' information needs¹ do not stem from externally assigned work and thus the awareness of an information need arises within them more authentically and organically. The planning that might be going on is perhaps closer to what Belkin described as an Anomalous State of Knowledge, or Taylor's visceral need (Belkin et al., 1982; Taylor, 2015). Patrons may not be fully conscious of an information need. It may come to them in the moment or be sparked by something that caught their eye during their visit to the library or their time spent on the library's website. Where academic and school libraries often work in collaboration with classroom teachers to provide IL support connected to a specific assignment creating a specific information need, public librarians position themselves to address information needs whenever and however they may be presented by patrons. Providing programming that would address how to understand and express those needs simply does not match the typical use of the public library.

This research shows that public libraries share some similarities in IL instruction with academic and school libraries in terms of the IL instruction they offer, but also differ in several key ways. We spotted similarities where public libraries addressed key components of information literacy such as evaluating information found on websites. But the much broader nature of public library programming which included everyday life skills, hobby interests, and an array of technology skills

¹ Here we use the phrase "information needs" in the broadest sense not limiting "information" to any particular format, product, genre, or type, nor restricting "need" to something formally and fully articulated.

deviates from the classically academic approach to IL instruction seen in schools and colleges. Public libraries understand that their constituents' information needs originate largely from situations outside the classroom. Public library patrons' information seeking motivations and purposes are more likely to be intrinsic rather than externally imposed by a teacher or an assignment. Both the topics of interest, as well as the level of mastery of IL-related concepts desired to satisfy their interest bring differences in the way libraries offer IL instruction.

We would not draw too many conclusions on this research alone, however, because it stems from only two types of instruction a library might provide, web-based guides and in-person programs. It is entirely possible that the majority of IL instruction in a public library setting might occur in one-to-one interactions between library staff and patrons. With that in mind, part two of our research agenda seeks to explore this through an empirical study of public librarians' experiences.

7 Future Research

After this initial broad exploration of how public libraries carry out IL instruction through passive and active instructional techniques, we seek to explore the issue from another direction by examining how individual librarians bring IL instruction to their direct interactions with patrons. Recognizing that IL instruction happens in more ways than just through web guides and library programs we will conduct a qualitative study with adult public service librarians to collect firsthand accounts of how they provide IL instruction when working with patrons. Participants will be asked to keep an online diary for one week where they will capture their daily experiences working with patrons. Through these methods we hope to identify in greater specificity the unique practices of public library IL instruction.

8 Conclusions

Public libraries in the US have a somewhat unique conception of information literacy as compared with academic and school libraries. The professional literature is less well developed, and less is known about how public librarians understand, value, and carry out IL instruction in their library settings. This research took a broad, exploratory approach to examine how public libraries provide IL instruction through documents and programming. More work is needed to understand the more nuanced, individual ways librarians may be providing IL instruction to patrons. As researchers move in this direction, it is important to develop theoretical understandings that most appropriately describe and support information literacy in public libraries. For example, some models and approaches currently in use are based on a deficit model of information literacy that supposes patrons are deficient in certain knowledge and skills that must be provided to them. We believe that public libraries may benefit from invoking a theory and praxis of information literacy that is based on the notion of assets, not deficits (University of Memphis, n.d.). Such a view of IL is oriented around individuals' ways of knowing and their lived experiences using information, as opposed to imparting a fixed set of IL skills (Todd, 2017). Not being bound by formalized IL structures may be an opportunity for public libraries to approach IL in new, creative ways (Chan, 2009; Partridge et al., 2008). With that caveat, the recently released Standards Framework for Learners by the American Association of School Librarians (AASL) may be relevant to public librarians' IL work. It juxtaposes six shared foundations (inquire, include, collaborate, curate, explore, and engage) with four domains and competencies (think, create, share, and grow) (American Association of School Librarians, 2017). The high-level nature of this model, coupled with an asset-based philosophy of IL instruction, may offer public librarians a foundation on which to adapt and create instructional initiatives that best

serve their communities. One size does not fit all and the unique characteristics of how information literacy may exist in the public library sphere merits more study and consideration.

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